

TEACHERS' PERSONAL QUALITIES AND STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN SAMBULAWAN NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL IN THE DIVISION OF EL SALVADOR CITY

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Teachers' Personal Qualities and Students' Academic Performance in Sambulawan National High School in the Division of El Salvador City

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Abstract

This study observed the process of determining the impact on students' academic performance and teachers' personal qualities. Specifically, this delves into the following research questions: (1) assess the extent of teachers' personal qualities in Sambulawan National High School in the Division of El Salvador City; (2) determine the academic performance of students when categorized as outstanding, very satisfactory, satisfactory, fairly satisfactory, and did not meet expectation; and (3) test the interrelationship between the extent of teachers' personal qualities and the students' academic performance. Moreover, the instrument used in this study was a modified questionnaire wherein the researcher analyzed, interpreted and reported the present status of the problem relating to students' academic performance and the teachers' personal qualities. The researcher used descriptive method in explaining, analyzing and classifying the data. Overall, the respondents described as always on the extent of teachers' personal qualities. Further, they described as always in the indicator that their teachers communicate them well. Similarly, the findings revealed that the respondents described always in their teachers show empathy and patience. Majority of the respondents obtained an outstanding academic performance. On one hand, few of them got a very satisfactory rating in academic performance. The findings revealed that personal qualities of teachers showed negligible correlation to the students' academic performance as indicated by no significance probability value. The select teachers of Sambulawan National High School in the Division of El Salvador City have highly manifested in assuring their students' to learn effectively. This concludes that the teachers are excellent in communicating effectively with their students. On the other hand, the teachers have highly manifested in exerting earnest effort to teach the students effectively regardless of some issues and concerns on their personal qualities. Most of the students in Sambulawan National High School in the Division of El Salvador City are excellent in performing their academic tasks and other school activities based on the required learning competencies. Upon the other side, few of them performed very well. This study concludes that the academic performance of the students and the extent of teachers' personal qualities were found not correlated. Therefore, the students could perform better in one way or the other regardless of some issues and concerns pertaining on the teachers' personal qualities.

Keywords: *teachers' personal qualities, students' academic performance*

Introduction

Students' academic and career success are attributed to the personal characteristics and qualities of an effective and efficient teachers. Teachers who can communicate, listen, display collaboration, adaptable, show empathy and patience inspire them to take a mile leap in their academic activities in school.

The framework of the study is bounded on the context of legal and philosophical underpinnings pursuant to Article XI of the 2021 Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers, which summarizes that "the teacher as a human being endowed with life, personal characteristics and attributes, which it is the highest obligation to live with dignity at all times whether in school, in the home, or elsewhere; place premium upon self-discipline as the primary principles of personal behavior in all relationships with others and in all situations; and, maintain at all times a dignified personality which could serve as a model worthy of emulation by learners, peers, and all others".

Teachers' personal qualities and characteristics such as patience because students have their own unique struggles; empathy, drive for self-improvement-they should be able to look at themselves objectively and see where they can improve, and adaptability are essential qualities and characteristics for effective and efficient performance of instructional leaders.

Francisco, et al (2020) pointed out that teachers' personal qualities and characteristics influence students' school and academic excellence. It was also found out that there was a significant relationship between teachers' demographic profile such as academic qualifications; content knowledge, instructional quality; teachers' job satisfaction; attitude; empathy; adaptability and the academic performance of students.

Further, Asio, et al (2019) espoused that the personal attributes and qualities of teachers affect their skills. In particular, instructional practices of teachers affect students' academic performance. It was also exemplified that teachers with excellent skills in the four language skills positively affect students' academic performance.

Moreover, Mercado (2019) found out that professional attributes are effective means of influencing students' academic performance. It showed that educational qualifications, teaching performance, teachers' behavior and professionalism significantly influence

students' school and academic performance.

In a similar investigation, Juan, et al (2019) found out that teachers' personal demographic characteristics such as the attitudes, empathy, and adaptability, concern for others, friendliness, appreciation, and drive for improvement positively affect students' academic performance.

Cadez, et al (2018) revealed that understanding of good teaching is based on teacher characteristics or personality traits rests in the relationships between teachers and students. Good teachers are surrounded by human qualities of understanding, self-assurance, regard for others, empathy, fair play, appreciation, adaptability, objectivity, interest, friendliness, maturity, credibility, trustworthiness, humor, polished delivery and ability to engage which allows them to influence students. Additionally, this ability to influence students is important since it is closely linked to learning and effective teaching.

However, despite of the teachers' awareness on the importance of afore-cited personal attributes and qualities of an effective teacher, there seemed to be an absence of concrete and systematic investigation on its effect or influence to students' learning. Thus, it is based on this account that the researcher is motivated to conduct this study to ascertain the influence of teachers' attributes and qualities to students' academic performance in Sambulawan National High School in the Division of El Salvador City for the school year 2020-2021.

Research Questions

The study attempted to ascertain the influence of teachers' personal qualities to students' academic performance in Sambulawan National High School in the Division of El Salvador City for the school year 2022-2023. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following specific questions:

1. What is the extent of teachers' personal qualities in Sambulawan National High School in the Division of El Salvador City?
2. What is the academic performance of students when they are categorized as:
 - 2.1. outstanding;
 - 2.2. very satisfactory;
 - 2.3. satisfactory;
 - 2.4. fairly satisfactory; and
 - 2.5. did not meet expectation?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the students' academic performance and the extent of teachers' personal qualities in Sambulawan National High School in the Division of El Salvador City?

Literature Review

Related Literature and Studies from the Local Setting

The study is supported by Article XI of the 2021 Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers which summarizes that "the teacher as a human being endowed with life, personal characteristics and attributes, which it is the highest obligation to live with dignity at all times whether in school, in the home, or elsewhere; place premium upon self-discipline as the primary principles of personal behavior in all relationships with others and in all situations; and, maintain at all times a dignified personality which could serve as a model worthy of emulation by learners, peers, and all others".

Lapuz (2019) revealed that teachers' personal qualities such as such as patience; empathy; drive for self-improvement; and, adaptability are essential qualities that are positively linked to students' academic performance.

In a similar investigation, Saguban, et al (2018) espoused that teachers' personal attributes and qualities arise from the theories of behavior and identification of behaviors of an effective teacher. It was further exemplified that teachers' behavior is associated with students' academic performance with the belief that teaching effectiveness arises from knowledge, behavior, skills, and experiences. The ability features were derived out of the Cognitive Theory of Bandura (1997) which considers the creation of meaning as important and when applied to teaching it emphasizes the intellectual growth of students.

Sagaya (2019) reported that teachers' personal qualities had progressively gained an important role in students' academic development as a result of its implications for teaching effectiveness, instructional practices, and for students' school achievements.

Further, it was emphasized that teachers with high levels of personal qualities had higher levels of job satisfaction and self-efficacy, lower levels of job-related stress and experience less or no difficulties in dealing with students' performance and misbehaviors. Caprara, et al (2018) argued that teachers with positive personal qualities have developed positive relationship with fellow teachers and students and at the same time inspire effective performance. Additionally, it was exemplified that teachers' positive qualities impact to students' academic performance.

Related Literatures and Studies in Foreign Settings

Teachers' personal qualities are linked to teachers' work performance and students' school and academic engagements. Good teachers

are goal achievers whether goal setting was their own or pre-set for them and linked to student learning.

Furnham and Grasha (2018) supported this view by stating that teachers' ability to create meaningful objectives, establish classroom environment, and specify student behaviors conducive to teaching and learning were classified as effective. This process product approach is debatable since student outcomes are measurable whereas teacher processes are not measurable. These realizations lead to the cognitive movement where Bandura (1997) enhanced the ability perspectives with the inclusion of teacher understanding in teacher effectiveness. Fuhrman and Grasha (1993) postulated that the compatibility of instruction and student understanding encourage the ability to be productive in thinking and problem solving in learners.

Saafin (2005) is of the view that students are motivated and learn in the presence of certain teacher behaviors and characteristics such as respect for students, thorough knowledge of the subject and good presentation skills.

The importance of teachers' teaching quality and the increasing evidence arising out of student evaluations of their teachers in the higher education context establishes the relevance of examining the vigor and deficiencies in the teaching of higher education faculty. However, the very idea of asking students to verbalize their learning experiences from the perspective of the kind of teaching they have experienced is problematic (Riasati & Bagheri, 2014), especially given the fact that the quality of teaching is a matter of concern and yet students remain reluctant to be very open about it due to their fear of receiving poor grades.

In a similar investigation, Lee, et al (2016) stipulated that other variables which take a good impact on students' performance. Accordingly, there was a significant correlation between teachers' personal qualities and student growth while controlling for teacher and school characteristics.

Given that the success of academic performance of students depends on the personal qualities of teachers and their competence, qualifications and engagements. Ibad (2016) revealed that teachers' traits in the domains of personality and ability as arising out of student perceptions of their teachers and classifying them as good or poor depends solely on their personal point-of-view.

Consequently, with this importance attributed to student views of their teachers' ability to facilitate learning, the objectives of student assessments of teachers are of benefit in terms of decisive feedback about teacher effectiveness. This would lead students to make appropriate choices of courses of study and faculty, permit academic administrators to evaluate teacher performance with a view to making forays in research aimed at teacher development and learning improvement (Marsh, 2019).

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized the descriptive- correlational research design. Descriptive research according to Calderon, et al (2012) is a fact-finding inquiry or investigation. It was employed to develop a thorough knowledge of the primary causes of the given situations.

In addition, descriptive design as an inquiry used an in-depth analysis of the problem which data collection methods include, but not limited to the survey questionnaire and the like.

Subsequently, descriptive research design was utilized to quantify the problem by way of generating numerical data or data that can be transformed into usable statistics. This method measures variables through the use of quantifiable or finite data and the analysis was based on generated information from statistical tools. This method was also used in an inquiry with larger population.

Successively, descriptive data gathering procedures comprise different types of gathering information such as, but not limited to, the use of adapted survey questionnaires.

Respondents

The respondents of the study will be the students of Sambulawan National High School in the Division of El Salvador City. There are sixty-four (64) student-respondents who answered the survey questionnaire on teachers' personal qualities. The respondents were purposively chosen for the convenient accessibility of the researcher.

Instrument

The research instruments utilized in this study was adapted from Francisco, et al (2020) who conducted a study on the teachers' personal attributes and characteristics and its impact to students' academic performance.

The research instruments composed of two major parts. Part 1 is on the extent of the teachers' personal qualities with ten (10) indicators while Part 2 is the students' academic performance which will be categorized as outstanding, very satisfactory, satisfactory, fairly satisfactory, and did not meet expectations.

Procedure

The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent through the recommendation of the Dean of the Graduate School and School Principal to conduct the study.

Subsequently, the same approval was sought from the parents to allow the researcher administer the survey questionnaire to their children and utilize the academic performance of students in the study. After the respondents provided the information, the researcher immediately retrieved the said questionnaire, summarized, tabulated, and submitted to the Statistician for statistical analysis.

Data Analysis

The following statistical treatments are utilized to analyse the data of the study:

Problem 1. Mean values and standard deviation were used to present the extent of teachers' personal qualities.

Problem 2. Frequency and percentages were used to present the students' academic performance.

Problem 3. Spearman Rank-Order Correlation or Spearman rho was utilized to ascertain significant relationship between the students' academic performance and the extent of teachers' personal qualities.

Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the research findings of the data collected from the study on teachers' personal qualities and students' academic performance. The main source of data is the survey questionnaire. The findings will be presented in relation to the research objectives stated in the study.

Problem 1. What is the extent of teachers' personal qualities in Sambulawan National High School in the Division of El Salvador City?

The teachers' qualities include various pedagogical skills such as skills in communication, listening, collaboration, adaptability, and the like. These qualities can be used in engaging classroom management, modalities, and exchange of best practices. Table 1.1 shows the mean distribution on the extent of teachers' personal qualities in Sambulawan National High School in the Division of El Salvador City.

Table 1. *Distribution on the Extent of Teachers' Personal Qualities*

	<i>Items</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
1.	My teacher communicates well.	4.93	.242	Always
2.	My teacher listens well.	4.78	.415	Always
3.	My teacher is thoughtful and kind.	4.75	.435	Always
4.	My teacher is interesting and engaging.	4.78	.415	Always
5.	My teacher shows empathy.	4.54	.505	Always
6.	My teacher has patience.	4.54	.505	Always
7.	My teacher values real-world learning.	4.91	.292	Always
8.	My teacher is personable.	4.67	.479	Always
9.	My teacher shows calmness.	4.76	.435	Always
10.	My teacher promotes love of learning.	4.82	.392	Always
	Overall	4.75	.412	Always

Legend: 4.50-5.00=Always/3.50-4.49=Most of the Time/2.50-3.49= Sometimes/1.50-2.49= Seldom/1.00-1.49= Never

Table 1 presents the mean distribution on the extent of teachers' personal qualities. An overall mean of 4.75 (SD= .412) described as "Always" on the extent of teachers' personal qualities which implies that the teachers are very highly manifested in assuring that their students could learn better. Thus, it is important to note to establish proper monitoring and motivational strategies. Fostering student motivation is a difficult but necessary aspect of teaching that teachers must consider (Yarborough & Fedesco, 2020).

The highest mean of 4.93 (SD= .242) described as "Always" in the indicator, "My teacher communicates well." This result implies that the teachers are very highly manifested in communicating effectively with their students. Thus, developing communication skills is necessary to maintain on the part of the teachers in order to attain best learning results from the students. Teacher communication skills have significant role in the academic achievement of the students (Khan, Khan, UI-Islam & Khan, 2017).

Moreover, the lowest mean of 4.54 (SD= .505) described as "Always" in the indicators, "My teacher shows empathy, and "My teacher has patience." These results signify that the teachers have highly manifested in exerting effort to teach the students effectively regardless of some issues and concerns. Thus, promoting professional development is deemed necessary to establish. Professional development that focuses on teaching strategies associated with specific curriculum content supports teacher learning within their classroom contexts (Darling-Hammond, Hyler & Gardner, 2017).

Problem 2. What is the academic performance of students when they are categorized as: Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Fairly Satisfactory, Did not Meet Expectation

The academic performance of the students involve various factors such as intellectual level, personality, interests, and motivation. This can be the result of learning from a specific learning objective. Table 2.1 displays the frequency and percentage distribution of the academic performance of students when categorized as outstanding, very satisfactory, satisfactory, fairly satisfactory, and did not meet expectation.

Table 2. *Frequency Distribution of the Students' Academic Performance*

<i>Students' Academic Performance</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Outstanding	17	52%
Very Satisfactory	16	48%
Satisfactory	0	0
Fairly Satisfactory	0	0
Did not meet Expectation	0	0
Total	33	100%

Table 2 discloses the frequency and percentage distribution of the students' academic performance. Result reveals that 17 (52%) respondents obtained an outstanding academic performance. This implies that majority of the student respondents are excellent in doing their academic tasks and other school performances and activities based on the required level of learning competence. Thus, it should be noted to establish effective motivational support and teaching strategies. The nature of motivation and learning strategy is vital to improving student learning outcomes (Gbollie & Keamu, 2017).

On the other hand, the lowest frequency of 16 (48%) denotes respondents who obtained a very satisfactory academic performance. This result indicates that among the students in Sambulawan National High School, few of them performed very well. This can be described that some students may be reluctant in doing their activities to be submitted on or before the deadline. Thus, teachers are suggested to promote collaborative learning strategy. Collaborative strategy has a positive impact on student learning and fosters social emotional skills beneficial for overall functioning in today's environment (Backer, Miller & Timmer, 2018).

Problem 3. Is there a significant relationship between the students' academic performance and the extent of teachers' personal qualities in Sambulawan National High School in the Division of El Salvador City?

The academic performance is the measurement of the various pedagogical skills of the students in attaining the learning objectives. Upon the other side, the extent of teachers' personal qualities described as their attitude and means in the fulfillment of their duties and responsibilities in the classroom and the students. Table 3.1 displays the test of the interrelationship between the students' academic performance and the extent of teachers' personal qualities in Sambulawan National High School in the Division of El Salvador City.

Table 3. *Test of Relationship between the Students' Academic Performance and the Extent of Teachers' Personal Qualities*

<i>Teachers' Extent on:</i>	<i>Students' Academic Performance</i>			
	<i>(rs)</i>	<i>p-Value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision on Ho1</i>
Personal Qualities	.082	.649	Denotes Negligible Correlation	Accepted

**significant at p<0.05 alpha level*

Table 3 displays the result of the test of interrelationship between the students' academic performance and the extent of teachers' personal qualities. Result reveals that personal qualities of teachers denote "Negligible Correlation" to the students' academic performance ($r_s = .082$) as indicated by the probability value ($p = .649$) means not significant. This implies that the academic performance of the students is not significantly influenced by the personal qualities of teachers. This means that the students could perform better in one way or the other regardless of some issues and concerns pertaining on the teachers' personal qualities. Therefore, it is important to consider other teaching strategies that would lead to the students into effective and meaningful learning outcomes. To inspire intrinsic motivation in students, schools should focus on nurturing their sense of autonomy, competence, relatedness, and relevance (Ferlazzo, 2015).

Moreover, Gieras (2020) stated that in order for students to want to learn, they must feel that what they are learning matters to them. Accordingly, understanding how a new skills or information is applicable to or will help them now or later on in life can make a big difference in motivation. Therefore, this present study implies that the null hypothesis is accepted as the result shows that the extent of teachers' personal qualities and the students' academic performance were not correlated.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the findings in this study, the following conclusions were made:

The select teachers of Sambulawan National High School in the Division of El Salvador City have highly manifested in assuring their students' to learn effectively. This concludes that the teachers are excellent in communicating effectively with their students. On the other hand, the teachers have highly manifested in exerting earnest effort to teach the students effectively regardless of some issues and concerns on their personal qualities.

Most of the students in Sambulawan National High School in the Division of El Salvador City are excellent in performing their academic tasks and other school activities based on the required learning competencies. Upon the other side, few of them performed very well. This study concludes that the academic performance of the students and the extent of teachers' personal qualities were found not correlated. Therefore, the students could perform better in one way or the other regardless of some issues and concerns pertaining

on the teachers' personal qualities.

Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the following recommendations are suggested:

The Department of Education (DepEd) should revisit the guidelines pertaining to teachers' personal qualifications. As such, they are recommended to effectively monitor the feedback mechanisms vis-à-vis the performance of the teachers.

School Principals and School Administrators are suggested to promote inclusive learning by adopting mechanisms to enhance the level of teachers' personal qualities.

The Teachers are advised to continue enhancing their pedagogical knowledge and skills by attending seminars, and other related activities. Aside from promoting professional development, they are recommended to apply effective motivational pattern, and the like.

The Parents and other Stakeholders are encouraged to collaborate one another to enhance the level of students' academic performance.

For the Future Researchers, they are recommended to deepen the analysis on teachers' professional and personal qualities in order to get additional input that would affect the academic performance of the students. Using other variables for the future study is likewise recommended.

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